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6 **Four-legged foes: dogs disturb nesting plovers more than people do on**
7 **tourist beaches**

8 Running tittle: Disturbance to nesting plovers on beaches

9

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17

18 **Abstract:** Recreational activities in nature have increased considerably in recent decades.
19 Human disturbance may trigger similar trade-offs in birds that the natural risk of predation
20 generates on productivity through parental investment decisions. In order to estimate how the
21 impact of human presence affects breeding birds on Mediterranean beaches, the behaviour of
22 incubating Kentish plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) was studied in relation to the approach of
23 people, vehicles and dogs. Observational data were collected and control experiments were
24 performed with a standardized stimulus. The response variability of birds in the decision to flush
25 from the nest was studied depending on the type of beach user, the location of the disturbance
26 event and thermal stress. Walkers, when accompanied by dogs, flushed plovers 93.8% of the
27 time when walking through dunes and 80.0% of the time when walking on paths, whereas
28 pedestrians alone flushed plovers 47.6% of the time when in dunes and only 12.9% of the time
29 when on paths. Lone dogs triggered a flushing response 100% of the time when they roamed
30 the dunes and 50% on the shore. The number of users in each disturbance event did not affect
31 the flushing behaviour. Nest return times were shorter on disturbed beaches, suggesting
32 habituation to the human disturbance stimulus. The ambient temperature for the nests in which
33 plovers flushed was lower and nest return time decreased proportionally with ambient
34 temperature, both suggesting that habituation to the human disturbance stimulus encourages
35 relaxation of the trade-off between escape behaviour to avoid predation risk and the effects of
36 thermal stress on unattended eggs. Females flushed more frequently (57.1%) than males
37 (32.0%), suggesting that they may perceive risk differently. Establishing buffers between nesting
38 areas and people may help birds habituate to the predictable and non-lethal stimulus of human
39 presence, facilitating coexistence between conservation and recreation.

40

41 **Key words:** *Charadrius alexandrinus*, conservation, flushing behaviour, habituation, human
42 disturbance, shorebirds, thermal stress.

43

44 Recreational activities have increased disproportionately in recent decades in natural areas
45 (Tablado & Jenni 2015). Humans are normally perceived as predators by birds, so the disturbance
46 stimulus may affect birds in a similar way to the risk of predation (Blumstein & Daniels 2005,
47 Weston & Elgar 2007, Tablado & Jenni 2015). Disturbed birds therefore experience an increase
48 in energy expenditure associated with avoiding the risk, which may decrease their fitness (Frid
49 & Dill 2002). Research has demonstrated that human disturbances can decrease parental care,
50 both in the incubation and chick-rearing phases, resulting in a decline in breeding success (Lord
51 *et al.* 1997, Ruhlen *et al.* 2003, Weston & Elgar 2005, Liley & Sutherland 2007). The behaviour of
52 birds in relation to human presence has often been used as an indicator of the impact of human
53 disturbance on natural habitats (Carney & Sydeman 1999). Understanding the mechanisms that
54 trigger responses of birds to the presence of people is essential for the management of natural
55 ecosystems that coexist with recreational activities (Tablado & Jenni 2015).

56 The flushing behaviour of birds against the disturbance stimulus is a complex phenomenon,
57 which can depend on multiple factors (Tablado & Jenni 2015). For instance, the type and the
58 behaviour of the subject that triggers the disturbance event are essential to determine the
59 impact on birds during incubation. Mobile or static subjects may affect flushing behaviour and
60 nest return time to incubation in different ways (Weston *et al.* 2011). Nonetheless, there are
61 other modulating factors on this behaviour, such as nest habitat selection (Montgomerie &
62 Weatherhead 1988), the detection capacity of potential humans that cause disturbance (Amat
63 & Masero 2004a, Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014), the distance at which the disturbance
64 begins (Blumstein 2003), the perception of risk (Tablado & Jenni 2015), species sensitivity (Holm
65 & Laursen 2009), sex, parental qualities (Conway & Martin 2000), physical condition of
66 individuals (Beale & Monaghan 2004), the simultaneous presence of predators (Weston & Elgar
67 2007, St Clair *et al.* 2010), the risk of thermal stress for the embryo due to overheating when
68 eggs remain exposed to solar radiation (Yasué & Dearden 2006a, Weston *et al.* 2011), or the

69 capacity of habituation to the disturbance stimulus (Nisbet 2000, Baudains & Lloyd 2007, St Clair
70 *et al.* 2010).

71 Dog walking is one of the most popular recreational activities worldwide and dog owners usually
72 let them roam free through natural areas (Banks & Bryant 2007, Jenkinson *et al.* 2009, Miller *et al.*
73 *al.* 2013). It is estimated that 20-30% of households have dogs as pets (Iloja *et al.* 2011). The habit
74 of walking unleashed dogs is a phenomenon that occurs worldwide, even in places with laws
75 and regulations that prohibit this activity (Williams *et al.* 2009, Schneider *et al.* 2019).
76 Nevertheless, there is a lack of evidence on the impact of dogs on wildlife, which is often used
77 by dog-friendly groups lobbying against pet control in natural areas (Banks & Bryant 2007,
78 Maguire *et al.* 2019).

79 Beaches are one of the natural environments in which dog walking occurs most frequently
80 (Bridson 2000, Colwell *et al.* 2005, Williams *et al.* 2009, Weston & Stankowich 2014). Beaches
81 support a higher level of human disturbance than other ecosystems (Defeo *et al.* 2009), so
82 efficient management of these natural areas is essential to maintain ecological processes and
83 the conservation of coastal wildlife (Schlacher *et al.* 2007). In this context, coastal shorebirds are
84 excellent models to study the direct and cumulative effect of human disturbance on bird fitness
85 and survival (Lafferty *et al.* 2006).

86 The consequences of human disturbance on beach-nesting birds have been studied mainly in
87 temperate zones (see for example: Roberts & Evans 1993, Schulz & Stock 1993, Lord *et al.* 2001,
88 Lafferty 2001b, Ruhlen *et al.* 2003, Weston & Elgar 2007, Lafferty *et al.* 2013, Webber *et al.*
89 2013). Nevertheless, there is a paucity of evidence on the impact of human disturbance in the
90 context of coasts under greater pressure from tourism, such as beaches in the tropics (Yasué &
91 Dearden 2006a, 2006b) or the Mediterranean (Oltra & Gómez-Serrano 1997). This is surprising
92 because the latter region receives about 320 million visitors a year, which comprises 30% of
93 global international tourism (2015 data, World Tourism Organization 2015). Both tropical and

94 Mediterranean coasts have a significant fraction of threatened shorebirds (Baillie *et al.* 2004,
95 Cuttelod *et al.* 2009), so more research is needed in this area.

96 The Kentish Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) is probably one of the best models to study the
97 effect of human disturbance on beaches. On one hand, its relative tolerance to human presence
98 allows the species to breed under different levels of disturbance (Oltra & Gómez-Serrano 1997).
99 On the other hand, Kentish Plover are in decline in a large part of the range, including several
100 countries in the Mediterranean region due to the increased human use of breeding habitats
101 (BirdLife International 2020), so it is urgent to adopt measures for their conservation.

102 In order to estimate how the impact of human presence affects breeding birds on
103 Mediterranean beaches, the behaviour of incubating plovers was studied in relation to
104 approaching people, vehicles and dogs. To this end, observational data were collected and
105 control experiments were performed with a standardized stimulus. The response variability of
106 birds in the decision to flush from the nest was studied depending on the type of beach user,
107 the location of the disturbance event and thermal stress. In addition, nest return time at the end
108 of disturbance was studied.

109

110 **METHODS**

111 **Study area**

112 This study was carried out in the Spanish Mediterranean coast. Four beaches were sampled in
113 the Castellón and Valencia provinces (Eastern Spain): Serradal (Castellón de la Plana, 40° 00' N,
114 0° 01' E), Almenara (39° 43' N, 0° 11' W), Rafalell-Vistabella (Valencia-Massalfasar, 39° 33' N, 0°
115 17' W) and Punta (Valencia 39° 18' N, 0° 17' W). The four beaches benefit from different types
116 of legal protection according to European and regional legislation. Punta beach is within the "La
117 Albufera Natural Park" and is also designated as a "Special Protection Area" (Natura 2000
118 network). Serradal beach is protected as a "Plant Micro-Reserve" and "Area for dune

119 regeneration" (local protection). Almenara beach is included in the " Catalogue of the Valencian
120 Community Wetlands " and protected as a "Plant Micro-Reserve". Rafalell-Vistabella is included
121 in the " Catalogue of the Valencian Community Wetlands".

122 At these sites Kentish Plovers nest primarily on embryonic shifting dunes and annual vegetation
123 of drift lines, but also in grasslands of small annual plants that grow on deep sand areas among
124 dry interdunal depressions. The four beaches are subject to different intensities of human
125 disturbance. Punta is a bird sanctuary with restricted access, where human presence is almost
126 negligible (managers and occasional trespassers). Serradal, Almenara and Rafalell-Vistabella are
127 beaches frequented by people for leisure (Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014). Serradal is a
128 beach frequented by people for leisure (>10 people/km/hour; Author unpubl. data). Almenara
129 and Rafalell-Vistabella have an intermediate level of human disturbance, with lower human
130 presence with regard to Serradal (1–5 people/km/hour; Author unpubl. data).

131

132 **Field procedure**

133 This study was conducted during two different periods. Firstly, research was carried out on
134 Serradal beach between 1992 and 2001 during each breeding season; secondly, between 2007
135 and 2009 in Serradal, Almenara and Punta; and thirdly, between 2015 and 2019 in Serradal,
136 Almenara and Rafalell-Vistabella. The same observer (the author) recorded all data across study
137 areas and years, so there was no bias due to variability among observers.

138 Kentish Plover nests were found by systematically searching beaches and dune systems from
139 early March to late July. See Gómez-Serrano and López-López (2014, 2017) for a detailed
140 description of the monitoring methodologies.

141

142 **Behaviour of incubating birds in response to human disturbance**

143 The response of incubating birds to different types of disturbance events caused by the
144 approach of people, dogs and vehicles (hereafter “beach users”) was studied in Serradal beach.
145 Those situations in which there was a nest approach of one or more beach users at a distance
146 less than 75 m were considered a “nest disturbance event” (Fig. 1). It was considered that there
147 was a response to the disturbance event when the incubating bird flushed as a result of the
148 approach of the beach user (hereafter “flushing”). Situations (categories of beach users or
149 locations) in which the flushing percentage was equal to or greater than 5% were considered
150 relevant (hereafter 5% flushing threshold).

151 Disturbance events were classified according to their location in 5 classes: shore, paths, dunes,
152 promenade and road (Fig. 1). The dunes category refers to the different habitats used by birds
153 nesting on this beach (semi-fixed dunes, shifting dunes, embryonic shifting dunes and tidal
154 debris; Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014); excluding the footpaths that cross them (included
155 in the category paths).

156 People were classified according to their speed in “static” and “moving” beach users. Bathers
157 and other users who stayed motionless for more than a minute were considered “static” beach
158 users. Three categories of moving beach users were considered: “walker”, “cyclist” and “runner”
159 (the latter included people skating). People walking on the beach were classified into two
160 groups: “walker” and “walker with dog”. Category “walker with dog” represented walkers who
161 were accompanied by at least one dog (all the dogs considered in this study were off leashes).
162 The category “lone dogs” represents loose dogs that roamed the beach without people nearby
163 (Supporting Online Information Fig. S1).

164 Two types of vehicles were differentiated: cars and motorcycles. For each disturbance event,
165 the number of beach users involved was recorded (e.g. the number of people walking together).
166 The Serradal beach is in contact with a road, a promenade and near to an airfield where small
167 planes and helicopters depart and land, so that it provided a unique opportunity to attain the

168 objectives of this study. In order to take into account the incidence of aircraft on the behaviour
169 of birds, it was considered as a disturbance event when the approach of aircraft flew over nests
170 at a distance less than 200 m (the distance it was estimated visually).

171 For each disturbance event, sex of incubating bird and the ambient temperature (measured in
172 the shade at 20 cm from the ground; Yasué & Dearden 2006a) were recorded. Nests were
173 monitored from outside the nesting area with binoculars and telescope at a safe distance to
174 avoid interfering in the behaviour of the birds. To maintain the independence of the data and
175 avoid interference from habituation to the disturbance stimulus, the observations were spaced
176 at least two days for the same nest, and only data from those nests that had not been disturbed
177 during the last hour were considered. For the same reason, only the first disturbance event of
178 the day recorded for each nest was taken into account.

179

180 **Nest return times**

181 The effect of human disturbance on the amount of time that nests were unattended was studied
182 using an experimental approach. An observer flushed birds off nests and subsequently recorded
183 nest return time (Yasué & Dearden 2006a). To standardize the disturbance stimulus, the
184 variability in nest approaches was reduced as much as possible (Van Dongen *et al.* 2015). An
185 observer (always the same person, the author) walked in a straight line towards the nest from a
186 distance of 150 m at constant speed (1 m/s), in order to avoid the bias associated with flight-
187 initiation distance (Blumstein, 2003). The direction from which the observer approached the
188 nest was randomized. When the incubating adult (usually the female during daytime; Fraga &
189 Amat 1996, Kosztolányi & Székely 2002, Amat & Masero 2004b) left the nest, the observer
190 started the countdown with a chronometer. When the observer reached the nest they stopped
191 for approximately 5 seconds and then moved away more than 100 m to a place with good
192 visibility of the nest. The observer waited (Yasué & Dearden 2006a) for the adult to return to the

193 nest and stopped the countdown when the incubating bird sat on the eggs. This elapsed time is
194 referred hereafter as "nest return time".

195 The experiment was carried out on both disturbed and undisturbed beaches. To avoid a possible
196 cumulative effect of humans' presence on flushing behaviour and nest return times, the
197 experiment was carried out only in those nests that had not been previously visited on the same
198 day. For the same reason, only the data collected from nests in which humans had not been
199 observed in the vicinity for at least one hour before the experiment were considered. Nest
200 approaches were separated by at least three days to minimize habituation to standardized
201 disturbance stimuli (Gochfeld 1984, Yasué & Dearden 2006a, Muir & Colwell 2010, Gómez-
202 Serrano & López-López 2017).

203

204 **Data analysis**

205 Statistical analyses were performed in *IBM SPSS Statistics 21.0* (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Binary
206 logistic regression models were constructed to analyse whether incubation behaviour was
207 affected by beach disturbance, with probability of flushing as response variable (binary variable:
208 "flushing" and "not flushing"). Two independent analyses were performed with the variables of
209 type and number of beach users, on the one hand, and location of the disturbance events on
210 the other hand as explanatory variables. In both cases, only categorical variables that exceeded
211 the 5% flushing threshold were considered. Additionally, interactions between type of beach
212 user and location were included in a separate analysis, since they are related and have direct
213 implications for management. In this last model, the explanatory variables used for the
214 interaction were the mobility of the beach users (binary coded as static and mobile subjects)
215 and the location of the disturbance events. In the three logistic binary regression models, year,
216 sex (binary variable) and ambient temperature were included as covariates.

217 Finally, a General Linear Mixed Model (LMM) was used to investigate the variation of nest return
218 time after the disturbance experiment. The member of the couple that incubated the nest was
219 considered in the model to test for sex-specific effects. Nest return time was used as dependent
220 variable and disturbance beach level (with or without disturbance), ambient temperature and
221 sex (male, female) as explanatory variables. Nest-ID was included as a random factor, because
222 female and male partners of a given nest are not independent. For the same reason, individual
223 Bird-ID was included as random effect to account for statistical non-independence.

224

225 **RESULTS**

226 **Flushing behaviour**

227 A total of 714 nest disturbance events were recorded. Of the disturbance events, 82.1% were
228 carried out by static or moving people (11.4% of the latter were also accompanied by dogs).
229 Cars, motorbikes and cyclists driving on the road and promenade did not flush birds. No vehicles
230 were observed driving along footpaths, dunes and shore during the study. The few events in
231 which small airplanes ($n = 9$) and helicopters ($n = 7$) flew over the beach at less than 200 m from
232 a nest did not produce a response in incubating birds (Supporting Online Information Table S1).
233 People on foot (mainly walkers) and dogs were the only beach users that flushed birds. The
234 number of beach users (people and dogs) involved in the nest disturbance events ranged from
235 1 to 12 (mean of 2.3 ± 1.7 , $n = 592$).

236 The highest percentages of flushing were observed when the disturbance event occurred in
237 dunes (65.9%) or paths close to the nest (24.7%). There was practically no flushing when the
238 disturbance occurred on the promenade (3.6%), the attached road (0%) or the shore (6.0%;
239 Supporting Online Information Table S1). The highest flushing rates were triggered by dogs
240 (100% of flushing when they roamed the dunes and 50% on the shore) and walker with dog
241 category on dunes (93.8%) and paths (80.0%). The flushing rate was lower for walkers (47.6% in

242 dunes and 12.9% on paths; Supporting Online Information Table S1). All dogs involved in the
243 recorded disturbance events were unleashed, so that the behaviour of birds could not be
244 observed when they were on a leash with their owners.

245 Beach users that exceeded the 5% flushing threshold (in all the 5 localization classes considered)
246 were static, walkers, walkers with dogs and lone dogs (Fig. 2). The logistic binary regression for
247 the type and number of beach users showed that only the presence of dogs influenced the
248 probability of flushing (Wald = 10.74, $P = 0.001$, $df = 1$, $B = 1.83 \pm 0.56$); the presence of dogs
249 increased the flushing probability up to 6.2 times. The model also included temperature (Wald
250 = 16.53, $P < 0.001$, $df = 1$, $B = -0.41 \pm 0.10$) and sex (Wald = 7.19, $P = 0.007$, $df = 1$, $B = 1.22 \pm$
251 0.46) as significant covariates. The probability of flushing was greater for the females (up to 3.4
252 times greater than for males; Fig. 3) and when the ambient temperature was lower (mean
253 ambient temperature for the nests in which plovers flushed $21.5 \pm 3.1^\circ\text{C}$, and $23.6 \pm 2.1^\circ\text{C}$ for
254 nests in which plovers did not stop incubation: Fig. 4). The number of beach users did not have
255 a significant effect on flushing behaviour.

256 The locations where the 5% flushing threshold was exceeded were the shore, dunes and path.
257 The logistic regression model for the location of the disturbance events included the shore (Wald
258 = 22.58, $P < 0.001$; $df = 2$, shore being the reference level), path (Wald = 15.63, $P < 0.001$, $df =$
259 1, $B = 2.64 \pm 0.67$) and dunes (Wald = 21.52, $P < 0.001$, $df = 1$, $B = 2.93 \pm 0.63$) as significant
260 variables, in addition to the sex of the incubating bird (Wald 7.18, $P = 0.007$, $df = 1$, $B = 1.15 \pm$
261 0.43), but not the ambient temperature (Wald = 3.62, $P = 0.057$, $df = 1$, $B = -0.16 \pm 0.08$).
262 According to the model, the probability of flushing of females was up to 3.1 times greater than
263 for males.

264 Finally, the logistic regression model that considered the interactions between location and type
265 of beach user included as significant interaction between the mobility of beach users (i.e. beach
266 users classified into two categories: static or mobile) and the shore (Wald = 29.39, $P < 0.001$, df

267 = 2, shore being the reference level), paths (Wald = 25.66, $P < 0.001$, $df = 1$, $B = 3.65 \pm 0.72$) and
268 dunes (Wald = 23.97, $P < 0.001$, $df = 1$, $B = 3.37 \pm 0.69$), with a greater probability of flushing in
269 these last two locations compared to mobile users. In addition, the interaction between the
270 presence of dogs and location was only significant for shore (Wald = 7.53, $P < 0.023$, $df = 2$) and
271 dunes (Wald = 7.53, $P = 0.006$, $df = 1$, $B = 2.38 \pm 0.87$), in both cases with a positive influence on
272 the probability of flushing.

273

274 **Nest return time after disturbance**

275 Mean nest return times after the bird flushed in an approach experiment was 213.0 ± 135.0
276 seconds ($n = 142$, range = 20 – 660 s). Nest return time was significantly predicted by disturbance
277 category (with disturbance, estimate \pm se: -69.952 ± 24.993 , $t = -2.80$, $P = 0.006$), sex (female,
278 estimate \pm se: 66.761 ± 33.398 , $t = 2.00$, $P = 0.048$) and the ambient temperature (Estimate \pm se:
279 -5.984 ± 2.808 , $t = -2.13$, $P = 0.035$). Nest return time was shorter in disturbed beaches
280 (mean \pm sd: 146.5 ± 131.2 s) than in undisturbed beaches (230.6 ± 131.1 s). Females returned to
281 the nest later than males after the disturbance experiment (females 179.8 ± 133.5 s, males 141.8
282 ± 95.7 s.

283

284 **DISCUSSION**

285 **Type of disturbance**

286 The spatial distribution of the origin of the disturbance was a determining factor of the Kentish
287 Plovers' response. Birds stopped incubating and flushed in response to the approach of people
288 and dogs when they roamed inside the beach, especially when they approached the nest
289 through dunes and paths. Nevertheless, the type of user was also decisive in modulating the
290 response of the birds. Plovers only altered their incubation against disturbance from the shore

291 if the dogs were present. This disproportionate response of birds to dogs was similar in all
292 locations evaluated. The fact that walkers were accompanied by dogs triggered an additional
293 increase in the percentage of nests in which plovers flushed (35.1% more on shore, 46.2% dunes
294 and 67.0% paths) highlights that dogs had an additive effect on the bird's responses (Banks &
295 Bryant 2007, Faillace & Smith 2016). Previous research focuses on how the response of birds can
296 vary depending on the type of predator and habitat, so that the response of birds can be
297 different in areas with more contact with people and pets (Seress *et al.* 2011). The results of
298 this study show a greater impact of lone dogs (higher percentage of flushing), compared to when
299 dogs were clearly accompanied by people. This suggests that the response to predation is not
300 necessarily general, and there may be different responses to specific predators and specific
301 situations.

302 Both humans and dogs are considered predators by shorebirds (Roberts & Evans 1993, Schulz &
303 Stock 1993, Lafferty 2001b, Burger *et al.* 2004, Le Corre *et al.* 2009, Webber *et al.* 2013, Weston
304 & Stankowich 2014). In fact, the occurrence of predation of nests, adults and plover chicks by
305 dogs has been documented in various breeding habitats (Nol & Brooks 1982, Fraga & Amat 1996,
306 Sanders & Maloney 2002, Amat & Masero 2004a, Diniz *et al.* 2016) and it is estimated that it
307 may be an important mortality factor (Montalvo & Figuerola 2006, Baudains & Lloyd 2007). Dogs
308 cause significant disturbance to birds when they approach them (Burger, 1981, Klein, 1993), and
309 have a stronger effect on their behaviour than people (Lord *et al.* 2001, Glover *et al.* 2011,
310 Weston & Stankowich 2014, Faillace & Smith 2016, Jorgensen *et al.* 2016). This difference seems
311 to be caused by the frequency in which pets chase birds and that dogs are instinctively perceived
312 as predators (Pfister *et al.* 1992, Burger 1994, Lima 1998, Lafferty 2001a, Miller *et al.* 2001).
313 Indeed, numerous cases of dogs chasing plovers have been observed on the beaches studied,
314 especially when plovers were performing distraction displays (Gómez-Serrano & López-López
315 2014, 2017).

316 People disturb birds when they approach them, especially as the distance is shortened and the
317 approach is fast (Lafferty, 2001a, 2001b). Birds interpret these situations in the context of a
318 higher risk of predation, and flushing behaviours are more frequent than in other disturbance
319 situations (Burger 1981, Burger & Gochfeld 1991, Blumstein & Daniels 2005, Weston & Elgar
320 2007). In this context, Lethlean *et al.* (2017) found that joggers evoke escape responses at longer
321 distances than walkers. Nevertheless, in this study it was found that there was no difference in
322 the response of birds to runners and walkers, probably because the sample of runners on paths
323 and dunes was smaller compared to walkers, due to the different habits of beach use.

324 The results suggest that the number of users in each disturbance event did not affect the flushing
325 behaviour. Similar to these findings, Guinness *et al.* (2019) found that the number of dogs
326 involved in the disturbance events did not affect the flushing behaviour of birds. Probably, the
327 frequency of disturbance events has a greater impact on birds than the number of people
328 involved. Previous studies have shown that at a high level of human disturbance, incubating
329 birds may have to respond to different disturbance events in short periods of time, which may
330 even overlap, greatly increasing bird stress. Weston and Elgar (2007), in populations of the
331 Hooded Plover (*Thinornis rubricollis*) nesting on Australian beaches, found that 17% of the cases
332 in which people disturbed nests, birds were already responding to another previous disturbance,
333 which extended the time of return to the nest.

334

335 **Trade-off between predation risk and nest thermoregulation**

336 The disturbance can have a major effect on bird fitness. Disturbed birds experience an increase
337 in energy expenditure associated with avoiding risk, potentially decreasing their physical
338 condition (Frid & Dill 2002) and reproductive success (Lord *et al.* 1997, Ruhlen *et al.* 2003,
339 Weston & Elgar 2005, Liley & Sutherland, 2007). This increase in energy expenditure due to
340 disturbance may be even greater when associated with the costs of heat stress.

341 The flushing behaviour of plovers was affected by the ambient temperature, so that the
342 incubating birds flushed less at higher temperatures. In the same way, nest return time
343 decreased as ambient temperature increased, so that birds returned faster to incubate in
344 situations of greater thermal stress. These results, similar to those observed in tropical beaches
345 (Yasué & Dearden 2006a), must be understood in a context of a trade-off between the risk of
346 nest predation and clutch thermoregulation.

347 The exposure of bird eggs to solar radiation on hot days may cause overheating in a short time
348 (Mayer *et al.* 2009, Gómez *et al.* 2018), but the gain or loss of heat that eggs may experience
349 depends on various factors such as ambient temperature, wind speed, type of substrate
350 (Saalfeld *et al.* 2012a), type and colour of nest lining (Mayer *et al.* 2009) and the variation in the
351 amount stored within it (Szentirmai & Székely 2004) or egg covering level (Amat *et al.* 2012). In
352 the studied beaches, the breeding period of the Kentish Plover coincides mainly with high
353 temperatures that can be lethal to unattended eggs. Heat stress may cause mortalities or
354 malformations in the embryo above 40.5°C in some birds (Webb 1987). The Kentish Plover is
355 one of the species of the Charadriiformes better adapted to thermal stress, since it has a wide
356 range of embryo tolerance against extreme temperatures (Webb 1987), supporting up to 42°C
357 before the egg's death (Purdue 1976). Nevertheless, in tropical, temperate and Mediterranean
358 climates, eggs can reach these lethal temperatures in a few minutes of exposure to solar
359 radiation (Bennett & Dawson 1979, Stoleson & Beissinger 1999, Conway & Martin 2000, Yasué
360 & Dearden 2006a, Weston *et al.* 2011).

361 The findings of this study suggest that disturbance caused by static users is greater than that of
362 moving ones, especially when people stop close to nests for long periods of time (Burger 1986,
363 Weston *et al.* 2011). Since most of the beach static users are represented by sunbathers and
364 they usually stop in the high and dry part of the beach, the disturbance occurs close to the tidal
365 debris habitat, which is one of the most selected by the plovers to nest (Gómez-Serrano & López-
366 López 2014).

367 The Optimal Escape Theory (OET) states that preys should balance their flight responses
368 according to the level of risk represented by a potential predator, so that prey starts the flight
369 at that distance where the risk of standing still and the cost of flight are equal (Ydenberg & Dill
370 1986). An alternative hypothesis known as Flush Early and Avoid the Rush (FEAR), postulates
371 that animals will flee as soon as they detect the predator in order to minimize the monitoring
372 costs (Blumstein 2010). Samia and Blumstein (2015), in a review of 178 bird species of 67
373 different families, find that FEAR hypothesis predicts flushing behaviour of 79% of the species.
374 Nevertheless, this last hypothesis does not fit with the flushing behaviour of plovers observed
375 in the studied beaches. Kentish and Snowy Plovers place their nests in flat places with little or
376 no vegetation cover in order to facilitate early detection of predators (Amat & Masero 2004a,
377 Muir & Colwell 2010, Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014). According to this prediction, it was
378 observed that although plovers were able to detect approaching people early, they flush only if
379 they were close to the nest.

380

381 **Sex differences in flushing behaviour**

382 Human disturbance may trigger similar trade-offs that the predation risk generates on
383 productivity through parental investment decisions (Frid & Dill 2002, Tablado & Jenni 2015). In
384 this survey, females flushed more frequently than males in response to disturbance events.
385 Consistently, females returned later to the nest after approach experiments. Taking into account
386 that females incubate the nest preferably during daytime periods (Fraga & Amat 1996,
387 Kosztolányi & Székely 2002, Amat & Masero 2004b), coinciding with the hottest hours, these
388 results were not biased by thermal stress, since the ambient temperature at which the approach
389 experiments was carried out were similar for males (mean of 23.1 ± 4.40 °C) and females (22.4
390 ± 3.5 °C; Student's *t*-test, $t_{140} = 0.73$, $n = 142$, $P = 0.408$). These results suggest that there should
391 be a different risk perception between sexes. Indeed, this bias in gender risk perception towards

392 the disturbance stimulus has been documented in phylogenetically distanced species (Frid & Dill
393 2002, Childress & Lung 2003, Symons *et al.* 2014).

394 Similar to these findings, in a previous study on these same beaches, it was found that the
395 investment in nest defence of Kentish Plovers (distraction displays towards a standardized
396 disturbance stimulus) was different within the couple, with a greater investment of females
397 (Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2017). Differences in defence investment between sexes are
398 frequent among birds, with females normally risking more, according to their greater
399 reproductive investment (Montgomerie & Weatherhead 1988, Møller & Nielsen 2014).
400 Nevertheless, in this study males invested more in nest protection, since they showed a lower
401 percentage of flushing during disturbance events and return faster to the nest. Although
402 daytime incubation of nests by males is associated with heat stress situations (Amat & Masero
403 2004b), there was a difference between the sexes when accounting for ambient temperature,
404 which does not seem support a thermal risk hypothesis for the differences. Since the energy
405 expenditure during incubation is similar in both sexes (Amat *et al.* 2000), it is likely that this
406 greater male involvement is related to the mating system of the species. The Kentish Plover uses
407 different reproduction systems (polyandry or sequential polygyny), being usual that days after
408 eggs hatching one of the members of the couple (normally the female; Amat *et al.* 1999) desert
409 the offspring to mate with another bird (Lessells 1984, Székely & Lessells 1993, Fraga & Amat
410 1996). It has been suggested that this mating system is due to the greater capacity of males to
411 protect the chicks and to the fact that females have a greater capacity to mate again (Amat *et*
412 *al.* 1999, Székely 1996). In a similar way, males may have a lower risk perception and greater
413 tolerance to stress caused by the disturbance stimulus.

414

415 **Other factors modulating flushing behaviour**

416 The response of birds to human disturbance is a complex phenomenon modulated by multiple
417 factors, but the way in which disturbance may modulate bird behaviour is not always intuitive
418 (Tablado & Jenni 2015). For instance, in tropical climates it has been observed that longer nest
419 return time in response to disturbance do not always have a greater impact on fitness. Yasué
420 and Dearden (2006a) observed that pairs that returned earlier to the nest had a lower
421 reproductive success, suggesting that other factors may be operating.

422 Flushing behaviour and nest return times are subject to various ecological, environmental and
423 physiological factors (Weston *et al.* 2011). Nest site selection may enhance or relax risk
424 perception (Montgomerie & Weatherhead 1988, Tablado & Jenni 2015). Indeed, nest
425 microhabitat selection contributes to the incubating bird's crypsis and, in turn, determines the
426 early detection capacity of the potential predators (Amat & Masero 2004a) or beach users that
427 cause disturbance. In previous research conducted on the same beaches, it was shown that nests
428 were located where the visibility of the incubating bird was maximized with respect to people
429 and dog-sized predators (Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014). These open areas are
430 particularly attractive to beach-nesting birds because they allow for a wider viewshed to observe
431 approaching predators or humans (Burger 1987). Additionally, nests that become unattended
432 after a disturbance may be more vulnerable to predation (Weston & Elgar 2007). It has been
433 described that the simultaneous presence of disturbance and natural predators may affect
434 flushing behaviour and delay nest return time in presence of visual predators, which could locate
435 the nest by parental activity (Martin *et al.* 2000, Weston & Elgar, 2007, St Clair *et al.* 2010).

436

437 **Habituation to the human disturbance stimulus**

438 The habituation to the disturbance stimulus is a mechanism that has been postulated to explain
439 differences in the decision to flee and nest return time in response to human intrusion (Nisbet
440 2000, Lafferty 2001a, Baudains & Lloyd 2007). In previous research conducted on the same

441 beaches, it was found that flushing distance was greater in the absence of disturbance. Similar
442 to these findings, the results of this study show that nest return times were shorter in disturbed
443 beaches, suggesting that habituation to the human disturbance stimulus encourages the
444 relaxation of the trade-off between the escape behaviour to avoid predation risk (Nisbet 2000,
445 Baudains & Lloyd 2007, St Clair *et al.* 2010) and the effects of thermal stress on unattended eggs
446 (Yasué & Dearden 2006a, Gómez *et al.* 2018). Nevertheless, given that climate change has a high
447 potential to exacerbate the impact that thermal risk can have on breeding success, more studies
448 are needed to better quantify the impact of a probable interaction between disturbance and
449 temperature after hatching.

450 Geffroy *et al.* (2015), in a recent review on the determinants of animal responses to human
451 disturbance, focus on the role and mechanisms by which habituation alters the way in which
452 animals react to natural predators, concluding that there is a domestication process that can
453 affect the demographic trajectory of a population. These changes can occur through direct
454 mechanisms, such as a lower density of predators as a result of human presence (Götmark &
455 Aahlund 1984, MacIvor *et al.* 1990), or indirect, since habituation to non-lethal disturbance
456 stimulus makes animals easier prey (Geffroy *et al.* 2015). For example, Baudains and Lloyd (2007)
457 found that the failure of the White-fronted Plover (*Charadrius marginatus*) nests in South
458 African beaches was higher in sites with less human presence due to the activity of natural
459 predators, but in the most disturbed beaches there was a high chick mortality due to domestic
460 dogs, since chicks flushed less because they were habituated to the human disturbance stimulus.
461 Other authors have documented, in contrast, inverse relationships. St Clair *et al.* (2010) found
462 that the flushing distances of nesting Two-banded Plover (*Charadrius falklandicus*) decreased
463 when human presence was high, as a result of habituation to the disturbance stimulus, but
464 increased in those sites where predatory mammals were present. It seems that the habituation
465 to the disturbance stimulus has limits in the case of dogs. This limitation would be related to
466 dogs' habit of making erratic movements around an owner, which influences three key factors

467 used by birds to judge the threat of predation: predictability, proximity, and speed (Glover *et al.*
468 2011, Weston & Stankowich 2014). Nevertheless, leashing reduces both the degree of roaming
469 and speed, which contribute to reduced bird response rates (Hudson 1982, Lafferty 2001a,
470 Weston & Elgar 2007).

471

472 **Implications for beach bird conservation and management**

473 Human disturbance management is the cornerstone of the conservation of nesting birds on
474 most public access beaches. In temperate zones, access restrictions around shorebirds nesting
475 areas are relatively common. Frequently these limitations are established through exclusion
476 fences, which are effective in mitigating the impact of human presence (Mayer & Ryan 1991,
477 Lord *et al.* 2001). These fences must be designed based on effective buffer distances (Weston *et al.*
478 2011), and managers often use the flight initiation distance (FID) for this purpose (Samia *et al.*
479 2013, Symonds *et al.* 2014). In addition to safety distances, the results of this study suggest
480 that the response of birds to human presence is mediated both by the type of habitat in which
481 the disturbance occurs and the presence of dogs (people walking dogs). The impact of dogs on
482 beaches affects both nest site selection (Gómez-Serrano & López-López 2014) and the
483 incubation and chick-rearing phases (Diniz *et al.* 2016, Maguire *et al.* 2019). For example,
484 Baudains and Lloyd (2007) estimate that eliminating the impact of dogs on breeding sites would
485 double chick fledging success.

486 Legal regulations that affect beaches in many countries prohibit dog access to beaches,
487 especially if they are not leashed. Nevertheless, non-compliance with these regulations is
488 common in very distant geographical areas (Dowling & Weston 1999, Lafferty 2001b, Colwell *et al.*
489 2005, Baudains & Lloyd 2007, Jorgensen & Bomberger 2014, Weston & Stankowich 2014).
490 However, even in regions where dog access to beaches is prohibited, there is social pressure to
491 legalize free access areas for these pets (Banks & Bryant 2007). The main problem of this

492 demand is that there is a conflict of interest with other types of beach users who reject this
493 practice (Maguire *et al.* 2019). In this way, local governments are moving the dog areas to the
494 most natural beaches, where the conflict with bird conservation is even greater. In the case of
495 Spanish Mediterranean beaches, this problem has been increasing in recent years (Supporting
496 Online Information Fig. S2), and areas for pets have been authorized on many beaches with the
497 presence of plovers. Anyway, if limitations cannot be established for dog access (at least during
498 the breeding season), leashing is considered the most effective way of reducing dog impact on
499 wildlife, even better than other measures difficult to control and enforce (Weston & Stankowich
500 2014).

501 An elevated temperature can have a potentiating effect on the consequences of human
502 disturbance, even making it lethal to eggs (Yasué & Dearden 2006a). Beach management should
503 be able to reduce the human presence in the hottest hours of the day during the breeding
504 season. However, these measures are difficult to implement in beaches subject to recreational
505 use, when high temperatures trigger precisely a greater presence of people on the beaches. In
506 this context, the most effective solution is the exclusion of access to people and dogs in the
507 vicinity of breeding areas. Setting boundaries between nesting areas and people helps birds get
508 used to the predictable and non-lethal stimulus of human presence, which facilitates
509 coexistence between conservation and recreational use (Burger 1989, 1991, Fitzpatrick &
510 Bouchez 1998, Ikuta & Blumstein 2003). The results of this study support management based on
511 the separation of uses, since the impact of human presence in some sectors of the beach (for
512 example the shore) had little impact on the bird behaviour. Managers of beaches that house
513 plover breeding areas should ensure that minimum control measures for recreational use are
514 observed during the breeding season, and especially that (1) dogs will not enter the beach, (2)
515 people will access the beach on authorized paths and walk alone along the shore and (3) people
516 who go to the beach for sunbathing will stay close to the shore, as far away as possible from the
517 nesting areas.

518 Another of the most suitable management strategies is the conservation of wide beaches, in
519 which birds can be kept away from people, which tend to concentrate around the seashore
520 (Medeiros *et al.* 2012, Murchison *et al.* 2016). However, this preference of shorebirds for wide
521 beaches (Patrick & Colwell 2014) is shared with beach users, who also prefer wider beaches for
522 recreation (Valdemoro & Jiménez 2006). This space-time concurrence between birds and leisure
523 is one of the main conservation challenges of coastal ecosystems, which requires an
524 understanding between local, economic and natural environment managers. It is clear that the
525 exclusion of one of the two uses (environmental or recreational) has costs not assumable for
526 the two sectors, so both are called to understand each other and the conflict must be resolved
527 through a long-term sustainable coexistence model.

528

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538

539 **Data Availability Statement**

540 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author
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803

804 **Figure captions**

805 **Fig. 1** Diagram with an example of the five locations considered in this study (the denomination
806 is shown in white boxes) regarding the origin of the disturbance events that could cause the
807 flushing of incubating birds.

808

809 **Fig. 2** Percentage of birds that flushed when disturbed according to the location and type of
810 beach user. For each combination the percentage of nests in which the incubating bird flushed
811 is shown. Sample sizes are given above each bar.

812

813 **Fig. 3** Percentage of incubating birds flushing in response to disturbance events according to the
814 sex of the incubating bird and the type of beach user. For each combination the percentage of
815 nests in which the incubating bird flushed is shown. Sample sizes are given above each bar.

816

817 **Fig. 4** Mean ambient temperature (°C) recorded when the incubating bird flushed or continued
818 to incubate in response to the disturbance events according to the type of beach user (walker
819 and walker with dog) and location (dunes or path). Walkers and walkers with dog included
820 records for shore, dunes and paths location. The dunes and path groups included records for
821 static, walker, walker with dog and lone dog beach user categories. Error bars show the standard
822 deviation.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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